

OUTCOMES OF 11 DOGS UNDERGOING PATELLAR LIGAMENT REPAIR USING AN ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE IMPLANT

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Purpose of the work

Patellar ligament (PL) rupture is uncommon in small animals (1). Surgical treatment is usually indicated, with conventional suture techniques being the most common reported techniques when reapposition of ligament ends is possible. Augmentation techniques such as transpatellar or circumpatellar sutures associated postoperatively with external coaptation (EC) or transarticular external skeletal fixation (taESF) are recommended to protect the tenorrhaphy. These surgical techniques have a fair to good prognosis (78% of dogs) with moderate to high complication rates (11% of cases requiring surgical revision). Transpatellar or circumpatellar sutures and postoperative coaptation or immobilization techniques have been associated with frequent implant-related complications (2). An ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) implant secured by sutures and an interference screw (IS), initially used for Achilles tendon repair (4), has been successfully used for PL repair in one cat (5). The purposes of this study were to describe for the first time the use of this technique and implant in dogs for treating PL rupture and document the outcome of this procedure. We hypothesized this technique to yield low complication rates and good functional results, associated with a normal PL length (PLL) on the affected limb compared to the contralateral healthy limb.

Materials and used methods

Medical records of dogs treated for PL rupture with an UHMWPE implant in 8 referral centers from February 2021 to November 2023 were reviewed. Surgical treatment consisted in performing a midline incision in half of the thickness of the cranial aspect of the musculotendinous junction proximally to the patella. This incision was extended through PL proximally and distally to the rupture site. The UHMWPE implant was sandwiched and sutured inside the quadriceps tendon and PL after re-apposition of the ligament ends when possible. The implant was inserted from cranial to caudal in a first oblique bone tunnel drilled through the tibial tuberosity and initiated at the level of the insertion of the PL, and mediolaterally through a second bone tunnel 5 mm-distal to the first one. The implant was then secured with an IS. Data collected included diagnostic modalities, surgical technique, complications, follow-up, and outcomes. The PLL/PLe ratio on operated and contralateral limbs were evaluated over time on each standardized available radiograph. Intra- and inter-observer repeatability were assessed by calculating the coefficient of variation (CV) for both PLL and PLe. After confirming that assumptions were met, an ANOVA was performed (n=38 stifles from 12 cases across 5 time points) followed by Tukey posthoc test for multiple comparisons to assess the evolution of the PLL/PLe ratio across follow-up.

Outcomes

Eleven dogs were included with one dog presenting bilateral PL rupture. No augmentation techniques such as transpatellar or circumpatellar suture were used. Eight dogs had no EC or taESF postoperatively, 3 had a modified Robert-Jones, including one with a splint. Follow-up duration was between 6 months to 2 years. Median time to return to normal limb function was 4 months (3-6 months). All dogs resumed to preinjury level of activity without any impairment except the one with bilateral PL rupture which showed significant diminution in the range of motion of one stifle. No major complication was reported. PLL/PLe postoperative ratios were significantly lower than the preoperative ratios and similar to the ratios of contralateral limbs. The ratio measured at short-term

follow-up was marginally significantly greater than the immediate postoperative ratio.

Conclusions

The positive functional outcome obtained here contrasts with those documented in the previous largest retrospective study. In this study, good results were reported in only half of the cases and poor results in 22% of the cases (moderate to severe lameness leading to a reduced quality of life or requiring medication) (2). No major complication and no repair failure were recorded in the present case series. In previous series reporting cases treated with conventional suture techniques, high complication rates were reported and were associated with augmentation suture failure, implant-related complication with taESF or bandage-related soft tissue injuries with EC. Minor complications, accounting for 37% of cases, were attributed to postoperative taESF or EC. Among cases without postoperative immobilization or coaptation, 66% developed complications, with half of them requesting revision surgery (2). We suggest that the lower major complication rates in our study are related to the fact that the UHMWPE implant and the overall construct were strong enough to protect the primary repair of the PL and that no rigid postoperative joint immobilization was required. Indeed, an *ex vivo* biomechanical study of gastrocnemius tendon repair using the UHMWPE implant showed better maximum strength than conventional suture techniques (4). The increase in PLL at short-term follow-up may be explained by the loosening of the implant at its proximal attachment in the PL, under the IS or by implant distension.

The retrospective and multicentric nature of the study are major limitations as case description and follow-up might be heterogenous and incomplete with lack of standardization of procedure and documented imaging.

In conclusion, PL repair was completed successfully in twelve stifles by using an UHMWPE implant secured with an IS. All dogs except one made a full recovery from PL rupture. The results showed that the surgical technique effectively managed PL rupture, in most cases without the need for augmentation techniques, postoperative immobilization, or external coaptation. Our hypothesis suggests that this approach contributed to a low complication rate and early functional recovery.

Bibliography

1. Witte P. Treating canine patellar ligament rupture. *Vet Rec.* 2014;175(15):368-369.
2. Das S et al. Patellar ligament rupture in the dog: Repair methods and patient outcomes in 43 cases. *Vet Rec.* 2014;175(15):370.
3. Morton MA et al. Repair of chronic rupture of the insertion of the gastrocnemius tendon in the dog using a polyethylene terephthalate implant: Early clinical experience and outcome. *Vet Comp Orthop Traumatol.* 2015;28(4):282-287.
4. Buttin P, Goin B, Giraud N, Viguier E, Cachon T. Biomechanical analysis of an original repair of an achilles tendon rupture in dogs: preliminary results. *Comput Methods Biomech Biomed Engin.* 2020;23(sup1):S52-S54.
5. Buttin P et al. Repair of Tendon Disruption Using a Novel Synthetic Fiber Implant in Dogs and Cats: The Surgical Procedure and Three Case Reports. *Vet Med Int.* 2020;2020.

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